

Transonymization of Uzbek personal names

Ziyodbek ABDULLAEV

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in philological sciences. Fergana State University

Abstract: This article is devoted to the transonymization of Uzbek personal names. Transonymization is the transfer of one noun to another noun group. In the article, firstly, the phenomenon of transonymization is studied in linguistics, and the transfer of personal names in the Uzbek language to other proper noun groups is explained with the help of examples of fiction and modern internet media texts.

Key words: transonymization, Uzbek language, reference, anthroponym, name, surname

Transonymization – the transition of proper names into other proper name classes – can be considered a special type of word formation. Superanskaja (2007: 46) understands this term as “the formation of proper names of all categories by transferring a known name to another onymic class”.

Transonymization or *onymic transposition* are used as name-theoretical terms in Slavic studies (Windberger 2021; Superanskaja 2007; Šrámek 2007). In German-language onomastic studies, such forms are not interpreted as the formation of new names, but as a change of reference class. Brendler/Brendler (2004: 416) describe such formations as "the transfer of an onymically used expression to name a referent of another name class" and Sonderegger (2004: 3438) as "the mutual formation of names from names".

In the following, transonymization is examined as a special type of word formation of Uzbek personal names. As can be seen in the figure below, the city name *Toshkent* is transferred to hotel, restaurant, wine, metro station or personal names:

Figure 1: Transonymization of the city name *Toshkent*

Superanskaja et al. (2007: 47 f.) does not exclude the similarity of transonymization with the metaphorical or metonymic use of personal names and states:

It is possible to exclude any connection between metaphor and metonymy, since in all these cases the route is about transposition of the name. Only metaphor and metonymy describe the purely conceptual nature of words that are not synonymous with one another .

In transonymization, only the name is transferred, not the meaning, whereas in metaphorical and metonymic name transfer, the meaning and similarity are decisive. However, one must not overlook the fact that a person who has the same name as a place usually has some semantic relationship to the place (e.g. place of birth).

Even when personal names are used metaphorically, names do not refer to a person, but to the characteristics typical of the name bearer.

(1a) Qizil kartochka haqida Messi nimalar dedi ?

(stadion.uz, last accessed on 12.03.2024)

(1b) Rossia matbuotida Eldor Shomurodovni tez-tez “o‘zbek Messi”si sifatida maqtalmoqda .

(www.stadion.uz , last accessed on 12.03.2024)

In (1a), the personal name *Messi* refers to the famous Argentinian football player. In sentence (1b), Messi appears as a name metaphor and does not refer to the Argentinian football player, but to the Uzbek football player who plays football like Messi .

In (2a) *Toshkent* appears as a city name. In (2b) the city name is transferred to the person's name.

(2a) Qo‘qon bilan Toshkentni televizorda ko‘rganman

(Tohir Malik 2017: 234)

(2b) Ovulga yangi ishga kelgan paylarim kechagiday ko‘z o‘ngimda , - deydi Toshkanboy og‘a .

(Ahmedov/Ziyodov 2010)

Transonymization can be distinguished:

1. Transonymization without affix
2. Transonymization with affix.

The first type includes those onyms that have changed their name class without affixes, such as

Guliston (female personal name) ← *Guliston* (city)

Navoiy (city) ← *Navoiy* (poet)

Names of many classes can be transferred to other name classes through transonymization . The following are common types of transonymization in the Uzbek language:

1	Toponym ← water body name	<i>Sirdaryo</i> (city)	<i>Sirdaryo</i> (river)
2	First name ← Toponym	<i>Guliston</i> (first name)	<i>Guliston</i> (city)
3	First name ← Last name	<i>Marks</i> (first name) <i>Ronaldo</i> (first name)	<i>Marx</i> (surname) <i>Ronaldo</i> (surname)
4	Toponym ← Personal name (pseudonym)	<i>Navoi</i> (Region in Uzbekistan)	<i>Navoiy</i> (poet name)
5	cosmonym ← theonym ¹	Venera, Merkury, Uranium, Neptune, Mars, Pluton	<i>Venus</i> 'Venus', <i>Merkuriy</i> 'Mercury', <i>Uranium</i> 'Uranus', <i>Neptune</i> 'Neptunus', <i>Mars</i> 'Mars', <i>Pluton</i> 'Pluton' (Theonyms)
6	First name ← Theonym	<i>Venera</i> (female name)	<i>Venera</i> 'Venus' (theonym)

Table 1: Common types of transonymization in the Uzbek language

As can be seen from the examples in the table, the transfer of names within onomastics can occur in different types. Here is an example from history: The founder of the Timuriddin dynasty, Amir Timur (1336 - 1405), named the settlements around the capital Samarkand after the world's largest capitals such as Paris, Vienna, Rome, etc. and the place name *Forish* - from Paris - is still in use today.

The transfer of surnames to first names is rare and usually such names only occur as one-offs. Surnames of famous people can be given as first names. Jakowlenko (2015: 287) has cited surnames that have been transferred to first names in the Russian language: *Amper*, *Benua*, *Bruno*, *Marks*, *Engels*, *Dantona*, *Lenin*, *Lenina*, *Rentgen* Etc.

¹The translation of the Latin theonyms did not take place directly into Uzbek, but rather they came into Uzbek via Russian.

Uzbek children also sometimes get their first names after the surname of famous people, such as *Marks* (Karl Marx), or after football players or other celebrities, such as *Ronaldo* (Cristiano Ronaldo), *Messi* (Lionel Messi), but this is also a rarity.

The second type of transonymization includes family names, first names and patronymics, which are transonymized using personal name-forming affixes such as – *yev* , *yeva* , -*ov*,- *ova* , - *yevich* , - *ovich* , -*a/ iya Karim -ov* ← *Karim*, *Karim -ova* ← *Karim*

Abdulla- yev ← *Abdulla*, *Abdulla- yeva* ← *Abdulla*

As can be seen in the examples, transonymization is the most productive type of word formation within Uzbek personal naming .

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